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Abstract:

The modular DAQ development projects Caribou (for silicon detectors) and SRS-VMM3 (for gas detectors) each provide a common open-source platform with re-usable hardware, firmware and software. This document reports on the achieved production and delivery of common readout boards for both projects, which constitutes D3.5 in month 42.

AIDAInnova Consortium, 2024

For more information on AIDAInnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

Caribou is a modular open-source data acquisition (DAQ) system developed and used within AIDAinnova and other collaborative frameworks (CERN EP R&D, DRD3, Tangerine) for laboratory and high-rate beam tests and easy integration of new silicon-pixel-detector prototypes. It uses common hardware, firmware and software components that are shared across different projects, thereby reducing the development effort and cost for such readout systems significantly. The common Control and Readout (CaR) board hardware designed at Brookhaven National Labs (BNL) provides resources such as power supplies, reference voltages and currents, as well as interfaces to various detector-specific chip boards housing the detectors under test. Within the scope of the AIDAinnova project, a new revision 1.5 of the CaR board has been produced and tested, and 31 boards have been delivered to the 9 participating institutes.

The SRS-VMM3 is a general-purpose, modular DAQ system for laboratory, test-beam, and mid-size experiments using Micro-Pattern Gaseous Detectors (MPGDs). It is based on the RD51 Scalable Readout System (SRS) and the BNL/ATLAS front-end ASIC VMM3a. The front-end ASIC is mounted on a readout PCB carrier, which can be connected to any detector using optional adapter cards. It provides signal amplitude and timing, is self-triggered, supports continuous readout, and offers high throughput in terms of acquisition rate (MHz/channels). Internal amplifier parameters, such as gain and peaking time, are adjustable, allowing integration with various detector technologies. As part of AIDAinnova, a full-system prototype was developed and validated in RD51 and DRD1 test beam campaigns at the SPS with different detector technologies. Access to the hardware is available through the CERN store and a CERN spin-off, SRS Technology. Different system configurations provide the flexibility to meet a range of needs, from laboratory tests to test beams and mid-sized experiments.

1. INTRODUCTION

Within AIDAinnova WP3, two modular open-source DAQ developments are pursued, targeting laboratory and test-beam measurements: the Caribou DAQ [1-3] is designed for silicon detectors developed in WP5 and 6, while the SRS-VMM3 DAQ [4-6] serves the gas-detector developments in WP7. The use of common hardware, firmware and software components that are shared across different projects reduces significantly the DAQ development effort. The system architecture, design and validation of the re-usable hardware components for the two projects is described in the WP3 milestone report MS11 [7]. This deliverable report focuses on the series production, testing and dissemination to the participating institutes.

2. PRODUCTION OF COMMON READOUT BOARDS FOR CARIBOU

2.1. CARIBOU HARDWARE ARCHITECTURE

Figure 1 shows a schematic representation of the hardware components included in the Caribou DAQ system. The core of the system is a Xilinx Zynq System-on-Chip (SoC) device hosted on a ZC706 evaluation board. The SoC combines a dual-core ARM Cortex-A9 Central Processing Unit (CPU) and a Kintex-7 Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) fabric connected through a silicon interposer. The SoC is connected via an FMC connector to the universal Control and Readout (CaR) board, which provides resources such as power supplies, reference voltages and currents, as well as interfaces to the detector. A custom-designed chip board implements the routing from a specific detector under test to the Control and Readout (CaR) board via a SEARY connector.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the Caribou hardware architecture, consisting of (from left to right) a ZC706 evaluation board, a universal CaR board and an application-specific chip board. From [8].

2.2. CAR BOARD HARDWARE REVISION V1.5

Based on the experience obtained from previous CaR board prototypes [7], several improvements were made for the design of the final production version v1.5:

- **Replacement of obsolete parts:** The bill of material was adapted to include replacement parts for components that are no longer available on the market, such as the I2C to SPI bridge.
- **Replacement of level shifters for CMOS I/O:** The bi-directional level shifters on the v1.4 boards caused distortions and ringing, especially when driving long cables. The 74AVCT245GU level shifters used in the v1.5 design are unidirectional, and a series termination was added to reduce signal reflections.
- **Small bug fixes:** Several inconsistencies present in the v1.4 design were fixed (gain differences on Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) channels, disconnected power rails and enable pins, inverted polarity of an LED indicating overheating).
- **Cleanup of schematics and layout:** various small routing and placement improvements were made to the schematics and layout.

The resulting final schematic and layout files of the v1.5 CaR board are documented and made available to the community in a public git repository [9].

To validate the design changes, a pre-series of five CaR boards v1.5 has been assembled and tested at BNL and CERN. Figure 2 shows the board layout and a photograph of one of the boards.

Figure 2: (Left) CaR board v1.5 front-side layout (from [9]). (Right) Photograph of a CaR board v1.5.

The tests confirmed the functioning of the boards and the effectiveness of the design changes. As an example, Figure 3 shows the falling edge of the output signals of the level shifter, comparing a previous CaR board v1.3 with the new v1.5. The distortion and ringing observed for v1.3 is no longer present for v1.5, confirming that the new level shifter design and termination work as intended.

Figure 3: Falling edge of level-shifter output measured on a breakout test board with an oscilloscope for a CaR board (left) v1.3 and (right) v1.5.

2.3. SERIES PRODUCTION AND TESTING OF V1.5 CAR BOARDS

Following the successful testing of the pre-series of five v1.5 CaR boards, a common purchase order for the series production and assembly of 31 v1.5 CaR boards was organised by CERN for the AIDAInnova community and other interested groups (9 institutes in total).

As a result of the tendering procedure, the contract for the supply of the boards was awarded to Safiral s.r.o [10]. The deliverables included the controlled impedance matching of the layer stack, PCB production, purchase of all components, assembly, basic electrical tests of the produced PCBs and an Automated Optical Inspection (AOI) of the soldered components. The production files sent to the supplier were identical to those used for the pre-series boards.

The production and testing at the vendor site were completed within 6 weeks. All boards were then received and tested at CERN, before they were distributed to the participating institutes. The tests consisted of configuring a target channel on the Digital-to-Analog Converter (DAC) component integrated in the device under test and measuring the corresponding output voltage using the ADC component on the CaR board. The tests were performed on all produced CaR boards and allowed functional validation of the CaR board serial links, voltage supply components and ADCs. Figure 4 shows results of the DAC scan test measurements performed using all 31 v1.5 CaR boards. The obtained results yield the expected DAC and ADC operation; therefore, all produced boards passed the performed functional test.

Figure 4: (Left) Terminal prompt of device under test powering and configuration using a v1.5 CaR board and custom test software. (Right) DAC scan measurement of the IBIAS channel on a device under test using all produced v1.5 CaR boards.

2.4. USER EXPERIENCE

All 31 v1.5 CaR boards have been delivered to the 9 participating institutes. Several boards are already in use for laboratory and test-beam measurements of pixel-detector prototypes, as shown in Figure 5 5 for the example of the H2M Caribou DAQ setups.

The improved signal integrity of the new level-shifter circuit has enabled the successful use of the v1.5 boards for the DESY ER1 test chip [10] and for the CoRDIA03 chip [11], which had not been possible with earlier board versions due to the distortion and ringing issues described in section 2.2. Including the recent AIDAInnova production, more than 60 CaR boards have been produced and are in use in the 14 participating institutes for more than 15 different pixel-detector prototypes with dedicated chip boards that have been interfaced to Caribou.

The flexible Caribou structure enables a large variety of applications in different domains. Example use cases beyond pixel-detector R&D include the implementation of a Time-to-Digital-Converter (TDC) for pico-second timing measurements [13] and a test system for ADCs interfaced to the Caribou hardware [14].

Figure 5: (Left) CaR board v1.5 in laboratory setup with ZC706 evaluation board and H2M device under test. (Right) H2M Caribou DAQ setup mounted on a rotation stage between the two arms of the CLICdp Timepix3 beam telescope at the CERN SPS test-beam facility.

3. PRODUCTION OF COMMON READOUT BOARDS FOR VMM3A

A prototype DAQ system based on the RD51 SRS (Scalable Readout System) and VMM3a (BNL/ATLAS NSW ASICs) was delivered within the scope of AIDA-2020 [15]. Under AIDAInnova task 3.5.2, developments specific to use in test beams for tracking and timing telescopes, as well as DUT studies, are being carried out. Key aspects such as distributed systems, compatibility with different detector technologies, synchronization, high throughput, flexible triggering schemes, data integrity, and a common DAQ have been addressed, aiming for a final design suitable for test beam operations. The results reported here were achieved in the context of the RD51 and DRD1 collaborations, with essential contributions from RD51 and DRD1 (H. Muller), the ESS-NMX team (D. Pfeiffer), the CERN Gas Detector Development (GDD) team (L. Scharenberg, K. Flöthner), and the CERN spin-off SRS-Technology (A. Rusu).

3.1. SRS/VMM3A HARDWARE ARCHITECTURE

Schematic drawings of a typical SRS setup are shown in Figures 6 and 7. The RD51 VMM3a hybrid, featuring the VMM3a front-end ASIC, is connected via Hirose connectors to the detector readout plane (strips or pads). The data recorded and processed by the VMM3a ASIC are transferred from the hybrid to the adapter card, which is connected to the general SRS Front-End Concentrator (FEC),

forming a single unit. The data are then sent via Ethernet to the DAQ computer. Synchronization between different FEC cards is achieved through the CTF (Clock and Trigger Fanout card). The system is inherently scalable to a large number of channels.

Figure 6: The RD51 VMM hybrid hosts two VMM3a ASICs (stage A) that are connected (stage B) to a Spartan-6 FPGA (stage C). Each hybrid is connected via HDMI (stage D) to the combination of a DVMM card and FEC card (stage E), which is shown here outside the Minicrate 2k. The FEC is then connected via Ethernet (stage F) to the DAQ computer (stage G).

Figure 7: Typical SRS Architecture: In the diagram shown, two different solutions are presented for multiple FEC readouts—via a switch or through a Scalable Readout Unit (SRU). Regarding the standard SRS and VMM3a architecture, each FEC# module includes a Front-End Concentrator Card (FEC) and a DVMM card [16] as shown in Fig. 6.

3.2. SRS/VMM3A TEST BEAM SYSTEM

Within AIDAinnova subtask 3.5.2, the activity has focused on the development of an SRS/VMM3a system for test beams, covering the required hardware, firmware, and software. A photograph of the

current prototype system is shown in Figure 8. The system has been tested on a 1-meter lever arm telescope with $10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$ active area MPGD detectors (triple GEM) for tracking, enabling position reconstruction with pointing resolutions of up to $40 \mu\text{m}$. Additionally, scintillators and PMTs provide track time resolutions of about 1.5 ns. The readout of the tracking detectors, DUTs, and scintillators is performed using the VMM3a hybrid.

Figure 8: The RD51/DRD1 VMM3a/SRS beam telescope. (Left) RD51/DRD1 telescope with DUTs, three MPGD detectors for tracking, and scintillators for timing and triggering. (Center) A tracking triple GEM detector equipped with four VMM3a hybrids (128 channels each) positioned behind two scintillators. (Right) Two SRS minicrates with two FEC-DVMM cards each (capable of reading a total of 16 VMM3a hybrids). A CTF (Clock and Trigger Fanout board) is installed on the minicrate to distribute the clock to all the hybrids connected to the various back-end cards.

3.2.1. RD51 VMM3a hybrid

The core element of the SRS-VMM3 system is the chip carrier. Figure 9 shows the hybrid version 4.1, which was previously developed and integrated into the current system. This hybrid was developed with the essential contribution of the SRS-Technology spin-off, which is responsible for the hybrid production.

Figure 9: RD51 VMM3a Hybrid Printed Circuit Board ($5 \text{ cm} \times 8 \text{ cm}$) equipped with two VMM3a ASICs, providing 128 charge input channels. A 144 pin Hirose connector on the hybrid connects to the readout of the detector.

A new revision (Rev 5, 2022+) was developed and tested in 2021. The most significant changes include the replacement of the Spartan-6 FPGA with the Spartan-7, the extension of the I2C bus to the detector connector (HRS), geographical identification of the chip, and the addition of new Flash

memory and ID chip/EPROM. All new production will use Rev 5, but backward compatibility with previous versions is ensured.

3.2.2. Back end

The back end of the SRS system is shown in Fig. 10. It consists of the Front-End Concentrator (FEC) card, the Digital VMM Card Adapter (DVMM), and the Clock and Trigger Fan-out (CTF) card. In the system prototype for the test beam, the cards are hosted and powered via the SRS 2k Minicrate. Each FEC card can read up to 8 RD51 VMM3a hybrids (128 channels each). A CTF can synchronize the clocks of up to 8 FEC cards.

Figure 10: The SRS DAQ system to operate the VMM3a FE ASIC.

The FEC contains a Virtex-6 FPGA for controlling VMM3a registers, reading data from the hybrids, and forwarding it to the DAQ computer. The FEC also allows for gating of the continuous data stream, effectively resulting in an externally triggered readout mode. This specific readout mode was implemented by colleagues from the Facility for Rare Isotope Beams (FRIB) at Michigan State University. It was successfully tested in two test beam campaigns of the DRD1 collaboration, enabling threshold reduction, data throughput optimization, and reduced storage requirements. Future developments with triggered mode implemented at the ASIC level may be considered for even further readout optimization.

3.2.3. External Powering for the VMM3a Hybrid

The VMM3a hybrid can be powered via the DVMM card through HDMI cables. However, due to the power consumption of the ASIC, an external powering scheme has been developed to reduce the constraints on HDMI cable length. In the latest version of the SRS system, external powering is provided by the Power BoX (PBX, formerly PMX-2 [17]), which has replaced the old Power-MultipleXer (PMX) card. The PBX provides power and ground return to the hybrid boards locally, next to the detector. It offers more stable system operation because it compensates for current spikes that occur, especially during the power-up and initialization procedures. In addition, it enables the

use of long HDMI cables (successfully tested up to 20 m). With this setup, a beam telescope with a 14 m lever arm was operated and read out during the first DRD1 test beam at the SPS in April 2024.

Figure 11: External Powering. (Left) Power box (PBX) for externally powering VMM3a hybrids. (Center) Power connection to the hybrid. (Right) Distributed systems with trackers located tens of meters apart from each other.

3.2.4. Synchronization with other DAQs

In recent years, we encountered several cases where the SRS needed to be synchronized with other DAQs. To ensure robust synchronization, a NIM Pattern Injector (NIP) box for the VMM front end was developed and tested. The NIP is essentially a passive, 2-layer printed circuit adapter for 128-channel, self-triggering VMM hybrids. The central part of the NIP PCB features a 140-pin HRS receptacle, allowing the hybrid to be plugged in either in the default position or rotated by 180 degrees. The top and bottom sides of the PCB are filled with copper connected to ground. Voltage pulses (default NIM) from the LEMO connectors are routed via very small 0.5 pF capacitors to the VMM channels.

Figure 12: The NIM Pattern Injector (NIP) Board.

By using this card, it is possible to inject an Event Counter into the VMM data stream, enabling unique identification of events. The new revision of the NIP will include serialized Event Counter injection for applications where the trigger rate permits.

3.2.5. μ ROC, a standalone and compact SRS system.

In parallel with the developments on the SRS-VMM3 system for test beams within the scope of AIDAinnova, SRS-Technology developed a new small stand-alone readout system for the VMM3a hybrid (together with colleagues from ESS-NMX). This so-called “ μ ROC” [22] allows for the readout and powering of two hybrids. It can be synchronized with the existing SRS hardware using the CTF card. For measurement purposes, it can be used for single-detector tests in the laboratory prior to test

beam campaigns. The μ ROC is also of interest for the test beam setup, as the time reference is provided by an additional VMM3a hybrid, which can be connected through the μ ROC without the need of using one of the available ports of the DVMM card.

3.2.6. Firmware

All available firmware can be downloaded from <https://vmm-srs.docs.cern.ch/firmware/>. Two versions exist: one for large systems (default, 44.4444 MHz base clock, 22.5 ns period) and one for small systems (40 MHz base clock, 25.0 ns period). From the webpage, it is possible to download both firmware versions: one for the hybrid and one for the FEC. A description of the current release of the firmware can be found at [18].

3.2.7. Software and Data Reconstruction

All the available software can be downloaded from <https://vmm-srs.docs.cern.ch/software/>. The required software tools are the control (RD51 VMM slow control [20]), the raw data monitor (Wireshark), the data acquisition for offline analysis (tcpdump), and the offline reconstruction and online monitoring (vmm-sdat [21]). All links and instructions are available on the webpage.

For the conversion and reconstruction of binary raw data into a ROOT file, the vmm-sdat software is used. It works for both single-detector setups in the laboratory for tests with radioactive sources, as well as for multi-detector systems like a beam telescope. Recently, the integration of the vmm-sdat output data into Corryvreckan [23] has started [24]. Corryvreckan offers a long-term solution for SRS/VMM3a test beam data analysis, providing stable support and a large community of developers and users. Although the integration approach required overcoming issues related to detector geometries (2D strips versus the typical pixel silicon detector geometry), the initial results are promising. Particle trajectories can be successfully reconstructed, and spatial resolution and detector efficiency can be determined with reasonable accuracy. Nonetheless, further performance evaluation is required, with integration efforts to be coordinated within the DRD1 community.

3.2.8. System Operation

Tutorial video and guide on how to operate the system are available at the following link: <https://vmm-srs.docs.cern.ch/operating/>

3.3. SYSTEM PROCUREMENT AND AVAILABILITY

The system is available and already used by the community. Around 30 groups from more than 20 institutes have expressed interest and have started using the system, with approximately 2,400 hybrids (more than 300,000 channels) distributed in the community so far. An additional 500 hybrids are currently in production. Groups that are interested in the setup can purchase it through the CERN store or via the CERN spin-off SRS Technology. The typical test beam setup allows for the simultaneous readout of three trackers and two devices under test. In recent years, several prototypes have been tested during system debugging, including a triple GEM prototype detector for AMBER, a Twin-TPC for the MIXE experiment at PSI, a μ RWELL detector for an MPGD-based DHCAL and various types of MPGDs for fundamental R&D.

With AIDAInnova and in connection with this deliverable, we plan to provide two independent systems for the test beam. This will consist of approximately 16 hybrids per setup, allowing for a total readout of about 2000 channels each. These systems will be made available during the DRD1 test beam campaign at CERN, as well as for external test beams if required.

Groups interested in the SRS/VMM3a system will find an overview of the necessary hardware in Table 1. Both single detector studies in the laboratory and multiple detector readouts in the test beam are presented. The system can be scaled up to a larger number of channels if required.

Table 1: Overview of the required hardware components for a minimal laboratory set-up and a minimal beam telescope.

	Laboratory test (single detector)	Test beam telescope (3 reference tracking detectors and 1 DUT with 512 R/O channels each, time reference)
RD51 VMM3a hybrids (128 chs)	up to 8 hybrids, typically 4	up to 16 hybrids (17 with μ ROC)
DVMM+FEC (8 hybrids max)	1	Up to 2
CTF (up to 8 FEC)	0	1 (for clock and trigger distribution)
Minirate 2k	1	1
Required in specific cases		
PBX (Ext Power)	1	3
NIP (EC Injector)	0	1
μ ROC (Compact SRS)	1 (2) alternative to DVMM+FEC	1 (for time reference)

The general SRS/VMM3a documentation can be found at the following link: <https://vmm-srs.docs.cern.ch/> [19]. In the hardware section, the link to all hardware documentation [17] is present.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PLANS

Two flexible DAQ systems, Caribou and SRS-VMM3, have been developed and produced for pixel- and gas-detector R&D. Recent common hardware productions for both systems have been organised successfully within AIDAinnova WP3.

Future work within the Caribou developer community will focus on the upgrade of the system to the high-performance Ultrascale+ FPGA platform and on a more compact and cost-efficient *System-On-Module* (SoM) hardware concept (CaR board v2.0), which is currently under design at Brookhaven National Labs.

The future work on SRS-VMM3 will focus on redesigning the SRS FEC for higher bandwidths (from 1 Gbps to 20 Gbps) and event-selection schemes on the new “eFEC” using the SoM approach. Compatibility with the VMM3a hybrid will be preserved. These activities will be carried out within the framework of Working Group 5 of the recently established DRD1 Collaboration on Gaseous Detector Technologies.

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
ADC	Analog to Digital Converter
AOI	Automated Optical Inspection
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
CMOS	Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DAC	Digital to Analog Converter
DAQ	Data Acquisition System
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
I/O	Input/Output
I2C	Inter-Integrated Circuit (serial communication bus)
MPGD	Micro-Pattern Gaseous Detector
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
SoC	System-on-Chip
SoM	System-on-Module
SPI	Serial Peripheral Interface